

PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF RAISING YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE SPIRIT OF PATRIOTISM

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Annotation: patriotism as the basis of commitment to universal values requires the coming of age of young people who are willing to sacrifice their lives for our country, and for our people, on the way to make our lives prosperous and free. One of the ancient Greek letters wrote in his work "To the honor of the motherland": "This is an old saying, but the truth is: a child who does not respect his father cannot respect the father of another, and a person who does not love his homeland cannot appreciate the motherland". How modern these statements are now.

Keywords: patriotism, Psychological Laws, the positive orientation of the individual.

Upbringing is a process of educational influence on the mind of the educator on the path of a specific goal in order to form a stable moral character and content of moral qualities in the educator.

In childhood and school age, an individual finds contentment under the destructive influence of upbringing. Upbringing as a special activity is distinguished by the presence of a specific program, or a perceived goal, from random or stitching influences of specially developed and justified means, forms, and methods of influence. It is known that the most important task of upbringing is the formation of strong beliefs and prejudices in the younger generation, as well as spiritual behavior based on them. This task can be solved only if the person relies on the knowledge of the Psychological Laws of the assignment of content with an active and specific purpose, as well as on the knowledge of the individual characteristics of the child.

The famous scientist Herbart advances the following points about the goals and objectives of upbringing. Herbart attaches great importance to defining the purpose of upbringing. He believes that the purpose of upbringing is to make up a person of good quality. Herbart believed that education without education would not be the greatest and main means of education to mental education in the work of upbringing.

Upbringing is given in a continuous way, first in the family, and later in educational institutions, together with education. The most important task of an individual's decision-making is to content the reader with beliefs and ideals that meet the requirements of morality. The further process in the formation of the reader's personality is that the system of moral beliefs and ideals that arise in it, that is, its spiritual consciousness becomes a dominant factor, a factor that determines its social activity.

In order to make up a positive orientation of an individual, it is necessary for school children to want them to behave correctly in all situations and situations, for him to behave correctly, for him to know what to do, he himself must practice full behavior.

It involves a sense of responsibility towards our country, as its citizens help it grow. A nation belongs to not only one person, but all, and we must work towards community good. Patriotism inculcates the sensation of pride and respecting the values of our nation.

Knowledge-without occupying a certain system of moral visions and concepts, khaki beliefs cannot be composed. In itself, this knowledge cannot have a significant impact on moral behavior without defining it. The most important way to find the content of moral consciousness is the way to enrich and generalize moral education with the emergence of proper behavior in the students themselves of course. The various district decrees on the moral knowledge of students, and the influence of a lively, bright fiery word on their minds and desires can greatly complement this work. Special Studies, as well as the experiences of teachers, show that all of the methods listed above are of great benefit in the field of moral education for students, but they should never become dry, boring, soul-touching, and exhortatory. Specific principles have been developed, and conversations about ethics must be structured on those principles. These principles are as follows:

Conversations about morality should be understandable to people of appropriate age in terms of content abstract and abstract concepts, it is impossible to allow themselves to be overwhelmed with complex concepts.

Usually, it is necessary to express the collective in which the conversation takes place, its orientation, the relationship of the members of this collective, the teacher's good attitude to study, and others.

Artistic conversations should not be held extremely often. It gives a very good result if conversations are held for concrete reasons in a row from an event

in the life of a country or collective to a positive or negative event in the life of a school.

The conversation is recommended to generalize bright, well-chosen concrete examples, starting with the analysis of facts and observations in life events or literary works, and moving on to conclusions.

It is necessary to rationally rely on a bright and touching image, which is presented in an emotional way.

It is important that it is proven that it thoroughly justifies the rules embedded in the minds of students. This is very important at the time of spending with adolescents and older students who are able to understand everything and agree to rational proofs to make sure that this is justified.

It is necessary for students to generate maximum activity or to arouse the desire to exchange ideas live, advance their opinion, and force themselves to think over moral issues. It is unsuitable for readers to forcibly accept ready-made excuses, conclusions about the norms of morality should be drawn with their active participation. To do this, it is recommended to prioritize the issues that must be put into discussion during the conversation process.

It is necessary to strive to evoke deep and touching emotions in students. In this, it can be achieved that the teacher conducted the conversation live in an emotional way, and not without indifference, enthusiasm, and pleasure. It is not to forget that the teacher passes on to students in his passionate faith

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